

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**SELF-SUPERVISED AND QUESTIONNAIRE-BASED STUDY
ON HIGH PREVALENCE OF ENERGY DRINKS INTAKE
AMONG SPORTSMEN AND STUDENTS OF MEDICAL
SECTOR****Dr. Mohammad Ammar Rafiq, Dr. Ramisha Rafiq, Dr. Farwa Ahmad**
Nishter Hospital, Multan**Abstract:**

In the few previous years, high prevalence of energy drinks intake among sportsmen and students is observed. This study was organized to find out this prevalence. The study was self-supervised and questionnaire based. Total medical students enrolled for this study were 233. Out of these, 121(52 %) students were involved in intake of energy drinks. The mostly consumed drink was Red bull and 101(43 %) students were timings to prepare for examination and to obtain energy were main causes of using this drink found in 34(14.6%) and 36(15.4 %) respectively. Medical students were using energy drinks on a large scale. Both friends and television were contributing in provision of information in ratio of 48% (113) and 66% (153) respectively. This is a need of the hour to make the young students and adults aware of disadvantage of intake of energy drinks.

Key words: Students, Knowledge, Caffeine, Energy drinks.***Corresponding author:****Dr. Mohammad Ammar Rafiq,**
Nishter Hospital,
Multan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Mohammad Ammar Rafiq et al., *Self-Supervised and Questionnaire-Based Study on High Prevalence of Energy Drinks Intake among Sportsmen and Students of Medical Sector.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

In order to remain active, make the mood fresh, remain alert, and gain energy and to get rid of sleeping mood, people used energy drinks [1]. The energy drink market is progressing very quickly after the invention of Red Bull. It is best brand among all energy drinks. In Australia and United States, its establishment is reported in 1987 and 1997 respectively. Now, there is availability of various types of energy drinks. Which also contain caffeine. In drinks, its quantity is from 80mg to 550mg per bottle or can [2]. About 140 countries, including Pakistan, are using those energy drinks.

In the few previous years, high prevalence of energy drinks intake among sportsmen and students is observed. To check out this prevalence, a survey was arranged in students of college in United States. According to this survey, in previous month, the percentage of students intaking energy drink (at least 1) was 51%. These students were using these drinks for different purpose. The main reason was to obtain energy, to mix drink with alcohol in party and to reduce timings of sleep observed in 65%, 54% and 67% students respectively [3]. In Turkey, similar survey was conducted in medical students. The percentage of students who used energy drink for one time was 32.6% [4]. The students of this college were using energy drinks and caffeine on a very large scale. These students wanted to get rid of depression. The percentage of such students in this study was 38.94% [5]. The objective of this research study was the check the prevalence of intake of energy drinks among medical students in Pakistan. The objective also includes to analysis information and understanding of these students about energy drinks.

METHODS AND RESULTS:

This research study was organized at Services hospital, Lahore. The time of conduction of this study was September, 2017. This study includes undergraduate medical students. For the collection of samples, the basis of study was considered. A written agreement was signed from participants which was approved by regarding sociodemographic features, usage of energy drinks was assembled through questionnaire. 39% was the percentage of students. Who were using energy drinks. The number of students in this study were 366, if using with 95% significance level and 5% bound an error of estimation. However, 500 medical students were selected for this study, the final number of students was 233 after management.

Using SPSS 21, information was assessed. For demographic variables and rate of intake of energy drinks such as intake, its causes and brand of energy drink, illustrative statistics which also include percentages and frequencies, were measured. The information regarding student's information about energy drinks and basis of information, was also collected.

Total students enrolled for this study was 233. 121(51%) students were found with consumption of energy drinks. Out of 121 students, the males and females were 80(66%) and 41(34%) respectively. 21.49 ± 1.692 years was the mean age of students. The most commonly used energy drinks were Red bull and string used by 101(43%) and 44 (16%) students respectively. The main causes of this usage were increasing study time and to obtain energy observed in 34(14.6%) and 36(15.4%) students respectively. (Table 1).

Table No 01: Energy Drinks' Consumption brands and reasons of usage.

CHARACTERISTICS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE (%)
BRAND CONSUMED		
RED BULL	101	43.4
STRING	44	15.8
MONSTER	7	2.9
BLUE OX	5	2.0
GATORADE	5	2.0
REASONS OF USAGE		
TO GAIN / REPLENISH ENERGY	34	14.6
TO REDUCE FATIGUE	24	10.3
TO REPLACE LOST BODY FLUIDS	8	3.4
FOR INSUFFICIENT SLEEP	15	6.4
TO REDUCE STRESS	9	3.9
BEFORE SPORTS / TRAINING	14	6.0
AFTER SPORTS / TRAINING	9	3.9
WHILE PARTYING	19	8.2
LOVES ITS FLAVOR	21	9.0
WHILE STUDYING FOR EXAMS	36	15.5
OTHERS		
JUST TO TRY IT	22	9.1
GOT IT FOR FREE	4	1.6

107(47%) students were aware of ingredients used in these drinks. Moreover, the presence of caffeine in energy drinks was known by 197(85%) students but they don't know the accurate quantity of caffeine. Just 8(3%) students know this. The information was given by friends and television to 113(48%) and 153(66%) students respectively (Table 2).

Table No 02: Knowledge about ingredients regarding energy drinks.

CHARACTERISTICS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE (%)
TV	153	65.7
INTERNET	33	14.2
FRIENDS	133	48.5
SCHOOL / COLLEGES	35	15
CLUBS	11	4.7
AWARENESS OF ENERGY DRINKS INGREDIENTS		
YES	109	46.8
NO	120	51.5
MISSING	4	1.7
AWARENESS OF CAFFEINE AS ENERGY DRINKS INGREDIENTS		
YES	197	84.5
NO	34	14.6
MISSING	2	2.0
AWARENESS OF CAFFEINE AMOUNT IN AN ENERGY DRINK		
YES	8	3.4
NO	220	94.4
MISSING	5	2.1

AWARENESS OF ENERGY DRINKS

AWARENESS OF CAFFEINE AS ENERGY DRINKS INGREDIENTS

Awareness of caffeine amount in an energy drink

DISCUSSION:

The usage of energy drinks has tremendously increased in the previous years. In 2012, four medical college of Lahore were surveyed to check the incidence of intake of energy drinks. In this study,

42%, students were found with consumption of energy drinks [6]. The results of this study were similar to our study according to which 52% students were found with energy drinks consumption. Illustrated by other studies, the percentage of boys in

consuming energy drinks was high as compare to girls [7]. In Pakistan, the most common and best brands are Red Bull and then string. So, students mostly used Red Bull and then string. Different causes were observed for consumption of energy drinks in different students. These causes include time extension for study, get rid of depression and to obtain energy. Studies conducted all around the world reported the similar causes. In Pakistan, a study was organized in medical college. The percentage of students who used energy drink to get rid of stress, for strong memory and attention, and for being active were 42%, 50% and 43.9% respectively. Similar study was held in University in Turkey. The common reasons for using the energy drinks found in this study were retardation of sleeping time, for being active and depression observed in 9.2%, 15% and 51.3% cases respectively [8].

The advertisement on television and information from friends contribute to high prevalence of consumption of energy drinks. So, students with young age were easily misguided and attracted to energy drinks. Half cases in our study were informed of components of energy drinks. It is considered that medical students are aware of health and nutrition. Accurate quantity of caffeine is known by some subjects while most of them just know that it is basic component of energy drinks. Another study was held among university students. In this study, the students that were aware of component of energy drinks were less than half [9]. All medical students of Pakistan were not mentioned in the study. So, results are not precise. But this study illustrated that medical students consume energy drinks on large scale.

CONCLUSION:

The ratio of medical students who intake energy drinks is very high. The support is mostly provided by friends. Same how, television advertisements also play some role. This is a need of the hour to make the young students and adults aware of disadvantages of intake of energy drinks. As, youngster can be misguided easily and attracted to energy drinks.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

In assemblage of information, help is provided by S. Ashfaq, senior administrative Assistant, AKUH Curriculum Office. And for statistical analysis, K. Nanji, Senior Instructor (Research), AKUH, helped us. We are thankful to both.

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